

COGNITIVE NEUROSCIENCE: ITS CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE LEARNING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

This article aims to present the contributions of cognitive neuroscience to the teaching-learning process. This is a bibliographical study. As a methodology, to carry out this study, analyzes were carried out in research in books and articles, published from 1988 to 2019, considering the main aspects and approaches on the contributions of cognitive neuroscience to the learning process. It was found that according to Neuroscience, learning and memory are different phases of the same progressive and continuous mechanism. The rapprochement between neurosciences and pedagogy is a valuable contribution for the teacher. For the time being, Neuroscience knowledge offers more questions than answers, but there are expectations that Neuroscientific Pedagogy is being generated to answer and suggest paths for education. Through the results of the research, it can be said that one of the challenges in the educational context is not just knowing how to teach or how to evaluate, but to present knowledge in a way that the brain learns and develops better. In view of the responses from the knowledge of neurosciences, there is a need for early childhood education teachers to develop methodologies and strategies for the teaching and learning process, with a view to improving the quality of teaching and learning.

Keywords: Early Childhood Education. Cognitive Neuroscience. Teaching-learning process.

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INTRODUCTION

This article presents pertinent information about the contributions of cognitive neuroscience to the teaching-learning process. From this perspective, it can be said that, currently, neuroscience presents its work proposals and studies about the learning process similar to what theorists such as Piaget (1979), Wallon (2008), Emília Ferreiro (1999), Ausubel (1982) and Vygotsky (2001), who highlighted different paths in order to achieve the objectives proposed in the teaching and learning process.

It is worth noting that these researchers based their theories on indirect evidence, through observations and interpretations of language, explaining how individuals perceive, interpret and make use of accumulated knowledge. Neuroscientists, on the other hand, seek to understand learning by considering behavioral experiments.

From this perspective, this study aims to present the contributions of cognitive neuroscience to the teaching-learning process. The aim is also to discuss the relationships between Cognitive Neuroscience and Early Childhood Education, thus enabling the strengthening of meaningful learning at this stage of basic education. The theoretical contribution includes studies by Carvalho (2009), Noronha (2008), Fernandez and Fernandez (2008) Lent (2010) and other authors, who developed research on the topic addressed.

This research is justified by its relevance in understanding the contributions of cognitive neuroscience in the teaching-learning process in early childhood education. With this study, we sought to answer the following question: How can cognitive neuroscience have a positive impact on the teaching-learning process in early childhood education?

Faced with the problem raised, this study is based on the search for theoretically based answers by renowned authors, who carried out studies on cognitive neuroscience, as well as contributions to the teaching-learning process in early childhood education.

The methodology of this study is based on analyzes carried out in books and articles, published from 1988 to 2019, considering the main aspects and approaches to the topic covered.

Therefore, the relevance of this study lies in the presentation of information that contributes to understanding the contributions of cognitive neuroscience to the teaching-learning process in early childhood education. In this sense, in search of theoretical foundation, we will present concepts about cognitive neuroscience, as well as its implications for teaching work, and consequently its implications for the teaching-learning process in early childhood education. And finally, the final considerations and inferences related to the topic of this research are presented.

COGNITIVE NEUROSCIENCE CONCEPTS

With a view to a better understanding of the topic covered, the concept of cognitive neuroscience is highlighted. To this end, Carvalho (2009) highlights that neuroscience brings together three areas: neuropsychology, neurophysiology and neuroanatomy, which have been classified as neuroscientific and which highlight, among others, the relationships between brain areas (neuroanatomy) and behaviors or functions (neuropsychology), sometimes trying to explain the underlying physiological mechanisms (neurophysiology).

In this sense, Kandel clarifies that cognitive neuroscience is a “[...] combination of methods from a variety of fields – cell biology, systems neuroscience, neuroimaging, cognitive behavioral psychology and computational science – have given rise to a functional approach to the brain called cognitive neuroscience” (KANDEL AND COLS 2003, p. 382).

This specific condition is due to the studies that could be carried out with the development of magnetic resonance imaging, which provided a better way of interpreting human behavior, through the visualization of specific areas of the brain that are stimulated and excited, according to the directed stimulus. .

According to Oliveira (2011, p. 34),

The term neuroscience is spread as a transdisciplinary concept by bringing together different areas of knowledge in the study of the human brain. The difficulties arising from different fields of knowledge, neuroscience and education, are diluted as each one appropriates the other's terminologies and seeks new knowledge (Id.; Ibid.).

The condition of observing the functioning and response of the brain to stimuli is more likely to be observed in the school environment, due to the impact of the systematization of information and demands that are applied to students. Added to this, the window of opportunity for learning is more intense in the period of childhood and adolescence, particularly in the first, because of brain plasticity and more intense formation of synapses.

In this sense, Fernandez and Fernandez (2008) clarify that neuroscience is the area of knowledge that provides an approach to the acquisition of information through experiences, building neural circuits, which are involved in human decision-making, such as: memory, emotion and feeling, judgments and thoughts that involve conduct and doubt in relation to what is learned and what is known, leading to new investigations of an empirical and theoretical nature, culminating in syntheses.

Lent (2010), states that cognitive neuroscience deals with the most complex intellectual capabilities, specifically, typical of man. The author also highlights that it can also be called Neuropsychology. Therefore, it is understood that cognitive neuroscience can contribute to the understanding of issues pertinent to the human learning process as a product of complex analyses, achieved through experience.

In this sense, Noronha (2008, p. 1) highlights that,

Neuroscience is and will be a powerful aid in understanding what is common to all brains and could, in the coming years, provide reliable answers to important questions about human learning, being able, through knowledge of new discoveries in this field, to use it , effectively, in educational practice.

Imagination, senses, humor, emotion, fear, sleep, memory are some of the topics covered and related to learning and motivation. The rapprochement between neurosciences and pedagogy is a valuable contribution for the literacy teacher. For now, knowledge from Neuroscience offers more questions than answers, but there are expectations that Neuroscientific Pedagogy is being generated to answer and suggest paths for education in the future.

It is therefore understood that neuroscience contributes to teaching work. From this perspective, it is important to highlight that the answers given about the knowledge achieved through research using knowledge from this branch of medical sciences help in the path of education.

NEUROSCIENCE AND ITS IMPLICATIONS IN TEACHING PRACTICE

In fact, it is known that discoveries focused on neurosciences do not apply directly and immediately in the school context, as their application has limitations, highlighting the knowledge about behavior that is necessary to infer deductions in the field of neurology and brain and its responses to direct and indirect stimuli. They provide information about education, but they are not dedicated to explaining it or presenting formulas that aim to guarantee results through experimentation. However, psychological theories are based on brain mechanisms linked to learning and can contribute to the choice of objectives, as well as educational methodologies.

According to Guerra (2011), teaching practice can be more meaningful and effective, as he understands how the brain works, which allows him to develop pedagogical strategies that are more appropriate to the ages and cognition potential of students.

Hardiman & Denckla (2009) show that in recent years, specifically in the United States, through neuroeducation, a new multidisciplinary field of knowledge and professional activity has emerged in the areas of teaching and educational studies.

According to the authors, the new generation of teachers needs to consider the knowledge acquired through neuroscience studies when articulating, planning and developing projects, which aim at the teaching-learning process.

From this perspective, Souza and Gomes (2015, p. 109) encourage that the teaching and learning approach is a task destined for the teacher, highlighting that,

[...] knowledge about Neuroscience can contribute, so that you know about your students' brain, how this organ processes knowledge, how it learns, and can also suggest interventions that the teacher should make with their children, because everyone can learn. Pedagogical actions in the classroom can become more efficient when people understand how the brain works. Although having this knowledge is not enough, it will allow teachers to better understand how their students learn and develop (Id.; Ibid.).

Therefore, it is up to the teacher to provide moments that promote meaningful learning and that are based on rich experiences through stimuli and encourage intellectual tasks aimed at promoting the activation of neurons, thus contributing to the production of knowledge. One of these ways is to provide empirical learning situations.

NEUROSCIENCE AND ITS IMPLICATIONS IN EARLY EARLY EDUCATION

Considering that in recent decades studies related to the process of cognitive development have contributed greatly to the educational context, this topic becomes necessary in discussions on teacher training. It is necessary to consider that cognitive neuroscience is related to learning processes, “which present different approaches to those that have already been found, often in contemporary schools, with regard to curriculum design, teaching and assessment” (BRANSFORD , BROWN and RODNEY, 2007, p. 19).

In contemporary times, it can be said that there are several studies that highlight Cognitive Neuroscience, specifically focused on the teaching-learning process. Alvarez (2015) states that this is an evolution in the educational context, especially in early childhood education. The author states that,

The brain's ability to reorganize itself, called neuroplasticity, is maintained throughout your life, but with advancing age, it decreases. Therefore, children have greater learning possibilities when compared to the elderly, although age should never be seen as an insurmountable obstacle (ALVAREZ, 2015, p. 36).

The brain is an optimized organ that develops functions always aimed at individual well-being. Human learning depends on experiences, on situational experiences, since this makes it possible to understand the situation itself and what should or should not be done, with there being a real reason to determine the action, whether objective or subjective.

Sousa and Alves (2017) highlight that motivation aimed at learning can be verified through direct observations of behaviors, the judgment of others, reports and self-assessments. Therefore, it can be said that direct observations are linked to the analysis of a student's behaviors, which could be indicative of motivational aspects that interfere in the learning process. As an example, you can put the student in front of some alternative activities and find out how they choose the task, considering their effort in maintaining and carrying out the action, as well as their persistence in the face of challenges.

Morales (2011, p. 6), highlights that “education is the central beam of interdisciplinarity that encompasses anthropological, philosophical, biological and psychological aspects of the human species”. Having said all this, what we have is that man is governed by phylogenetic and ontogenetic inheritances that must be analyzed and interpreted, each of them in their specific way of manifesting themselves in each individual and in each collective.

Araújo (2008, p. 8) argues that,

The process of forming social representations has as its principle the familiarization of what is unknown to the group. Facts, people or legal laws, for example, that are unfamiliar, that are part of the group's daily life, interfering in some way with relationships, need to become familiar. With this objective, they will be coded, analyzed and assimilated to previously known data, to be finally understood, becoming familiar to the group. This familiarity will be permeated by the elements given by the group, be peculiar and not necessarily similar to the *original form* of these unfamiliar facts or how they are perceived in other groups.

Therefore, the skills and abilities related to learning are associated with the context in which the child is inserted. Therefore, based on Araújo (2008), understanding the world is not only a necessity, but when seeking knowledge about social representations they take shape and, subsequently, everyday life becomes more stimulated due to its agility in variations.

Aristotle (384-322 ane) states that all knowledge passes through the senses.¹⁰ Vygotsky (1896-1934) expanded this concept by stating that between teaching and learning there is learning, which corresponds to the process and this will take place through interaction [not only *social but also through various forms of contact with reality*]. When a child speaks out loud

¹⁰ Cf. _ in this regard Aristotle. *The politics*. São Paulo: Escala, 2007.

about a task he is performing, exposing the difficulties he has seen and observed and the possible solutions, he is not speaking in vain, he is internalizing and reinforcing the entire sensory complex through speech and hearing. Primates have the intelligence and inventive capacity to perform simple tasks. It is known that, when young, they learn by observing and imitating their elders and, as they grow up, they continue in the same way; and everywhere men learned and sometimes learn a trade by the same method.

THE TEACHING AND LEARNING PROCESS IN EARLY EARLY EDUCATION

Considering the teaching and learning process in early childhood education, Marcilio (1998, p. 50) argues that Brazil precedes the precepts of the Convention, recognizing that the child has rights, as provided for in the 1988 Constitution, set out in article 227 of the Magna Carta :

It is the duty of the family, society and the State to guarantee to children and adolescents, with absolute priority, the right to life, health, food, education, leisure, professionalization, culture, dignity, respect, freedom and family and community coexistence, in addition to keeping it safe from all forms of neglect, discrimination, exploitation, violence, cruelty and oppression (Id.; Ibid.).

In this sense, it is clear that the 1988 Federal Constitution recognizes that children have the right to regular school education. According to the Magna Carta, it is the State's duty to guarantee care in daycare centers and preschools for children aged 0 to 6 years. However, Soares (1999, p. 78) highlights that,

In the 19th century, the child was recognized as a social category with protection needs, especially due to the contributions of the sciences of Pedagogy, Psychology and Medicine. However, it was in the 20th century that new meanings were attributed to childhood, through a new awareness that children were essential human sources, on whose maturational dimension the future of society would depend (Id.; Ibid.).

For Kramer (2006), as young children are inserted into the educational context, they have the possibility of being included as active participants in society, since, being a complete being as a human being, who asks, answers, learns, but, in addition, also teaches.

For Weigel (1998),

Cognitive/linguistic development: the child's source of knowledge is the situations they have the opportunity to experience in their daily lives. Therefore, the greater the wealth of stimuli she receives, the better her

intellectual development will be. (...) Psychomotor development: musical activities offer countless opportunities for children to improve their motor skills, learn to control their muscles and move with ease. Rhythm plays an important role in the formation and balance of the nervous system. (...) Socio-affective development: the child gradually forms their identity, perceiving themselves as different from others and at the same time seeking to integrate with others. In this process, self-esteem and self-realization play a very important role (Idem, p. 23).

The need for competence can be nurtured by presenting challenges appropriate to students' developmental level and providing feedback about their performance.

Cury (1998) contributes by stating that Early Childhood Education still has a long way to go so that school institutions become spaces for promoting and defending children's citizenship.

CONCLUSION

Based on the studies carried out, it can be seen that cognitive neuroscience contributes to the teaching-learning process in early childhood education. In this sense, the considerations made throughout this research indicate that cognitive neuroscience does not offer recipes for results in the educational context of early childhood education, but provides information related to the process of development of human learning.

Given the answers from neuroscience knowledge, there is a need for early childhood education teachers to develop methodologies and strategies for the teaching and learning process, with a view to improving the quality of teaching. Therefore, early childhood education teachers' knowledge of cognitive neuroscience is essential.

With this study, it was also found that, according to Neuroscience, learning and memory are different phases of the same progressive and continuous mechanism. Based on the research results, it can be said that the challenge for education is not just knowing how to teach or how to evaluate, but presenting knowledge in a way in which the brain learns better.

It is worth highlighting that Cognitive Neuroscience, despite being a relatively recent scientific branch, will certainly consolidate itself as a field of interest for all subjects involved with teaching and learning, that is, for students, teachers, pedagogues and other actors linked to the educational space.

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